

THE IMPORTANCE OF INCREASING THE ACTIVITY AND MOTIVATION OF FUTURE VOCATIONAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564850>

Raximov Zokir Toshtemirovich

Professor of the Pedagogical institute of Karshi state university, doctor of pedagogical sciences, academician of the Turan academy of sciences

Badalova Rushana

Master of the Pedagogical institute of Karshi state university

Annotation. *This article presents a number of ideas as mechanisms for increasing the activity of students in the field of vocational education, as well as the purpose, content, types of educational activities of students, the diversity of the educational process in which they are involved, student activity, independence, cognitive activity as a process has an imitative, reproductive, exploratory, creative nature, the content of the organization of educational activities, the result, the content and analysis of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.*

Keywords: education, process, profession, student, activity, activity, motive, quality, result, formation.

Today, the work on radical improvement of the education system in our country, the creation of a strong organizational and legal mechanism for the development of worthy successors of our future is gaining momentum. The pace of global development, like all other spheres, requires a new approach to the educational process, the introduction of innovative technologies. Accordingly, educating the younger generation to be physically healthy, intellectually developed, independent-minded, strong-willed, loyal to the motherland, deepen democratic reforms and increase their social activity in the development of civil society are important tasks. Consequently, the development of any state and society is inextricably linked with the maturity, aspirations and courage of the younger generation. In this regard, the steady increase in investments from the state budget in the social sphere, including the reform of the education system, the training of highly qualified personnel in the field of education laws and state programs, ensuring the effective integration of science and industry, educating young people in the spirit of national and universal values. the success of the tasks is particularly noteworthy.

The state policy in the field of training is based on the formation of a comprehensively developed person - a citizen through a system of continuous education, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual and

spiritual and moral upbringing of man. Therefore, one of the main requirements for the teacher is to form in students the motivation to study.

It is well known that motivation is a psychological factor that is the source, cause, evidence, and various possibilities of student activity. It is a powerful tool that encourages students to work hard to learn the basics of knowledge, skills, specialties with enthusiasm and interest. That is, motivation is the purposeful orientation of students in psychological (spiritual) ways to increase their activity in learning. It is related to the satisfaction of a specific need [1]. And need is manifested in causes, because need is a motive that drives people to action. At the same time, there is a need to shape the need for students to acquire knowledge. The task of the teacher is, on the one hand, to find ways to form the need for knowledge in students, to find and apply them in the learning process, and on the other hand, to improve and coordinate the activities to meet the need for knowledge. In order to increase the activity of students in the process of acquiring knowledge, it is expedient to form the inclinations, interests and needs.

Although the activity of students in higher education institutions seems to represent two separate process states, it is an indicator of the behavior that occurs in a holistic, whole process based on the mutual integration between them [2]. The emergence of activity in students, on the one hand, represents the effectiveness of education, as well as the result of pedagogical activities aimed at its formation. The formation of student activity in higher education institutions also indicates the training of a qualified specialist in the conditions of market relations.

It is known that the subject of educational activity in higher education institutions is a student. Therefore, in the center of education with a socio-pedagogical basis lies its personality, consciousness, as well as the relationship between the world under study and its partners in educational activities: students, teachers who organize and direct their education. This issue has been equally important at all times.

The activity of the student is reflected in his intellectual reflection in the process of learning, in the performance of general and individual tasks [3]. These features not only ensure that students receive a high level of knowledge, but also are characteristic of his vital activity, that is, the formation of the student's personality, his active attitude to practice, to life. Therefore, it is safe to say that the development of learning activity is the formation of an active life outlook of the individual.

Another distinctive aspect of the educational activity of students of higher education institutions is that it has a specific organizational content.

As the purpose, content and types of educational activities of students are included in the program, the educational process in which they are involved is different; subject (student) power can go with activity, independence, different spending. In some cases, students' learning activities as a process can be simulated, reproductive (productive), exploratory, creative in nature. The content of the organization of educational activities affects the final result - the nature of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities [4, 5, 6].

The following can be considered as mechanisms to increase the activity of students in the acquisition of knowledge:

1) the training sessions should be organized in such a way that they allow the teacher to communicate more with each other;

2) it is important to be able to answer questions of interest to students on the topic without delaying the end of the lesson, even if the question is not directly related to the topic;

3) to appreciate and encourage any achievements of students in reading and learning;

4) not to misinterpret the answers and to create conditions for the student to fully use their abilities, to demonstrate their knowledge;

5) develop their initiative and encourage it by available means;

6) prevent students from remaining in a passive observer position when using technical means of teaching, effective use of modern, interactive methods of teaching;

7) Strict adherence to the principle of fairness in the assessment of students' knowledge. Unless students are rewarded for their hard work and ability, their intellectual intelligence, they will not try to acquire active knowledge.

8) to convey the content of education in the volume and complexity that students receive at the level of mental ability;

9) the position of the teacher: - hardship, rigidity, if necessary, negligence (to some shortcomings of the student), relative impartiality, demanding, cheerful, professional knowledge, pedagogical ability. On the contrary, arrogance, nervousness, lowering of rating points, paperwork, excessive exhortation, dissatisfaction with the deans lead to nervousness of students and increase their stubbornness, leading to a decrease in their activity in education. The complexity of the teacher's work lies in the fact that he is able to find a way to the heart of each student, to create conditions for the development of opportunities in each individual [7, 8, 9, 10].

Nowadays, curricula start with a short practical knowledge and then suddenly with practical training. In fact, it would be right to move on to practical training only if you know the theory well. Only then will students have a desire to expand and deepen their knowledge.

In order to increase students' interest in learning, the existing problems should be studied, divided into groups by specialization, brought to the attention of students with proposals for solutions on specific topics, ways to motivate students who have found a significant solution to the problem. This method also helps to increase students' interest and activity in reading [11].

The teacher must know the latest scientific ideas, scientific achievements. If each time the new source of information is the students themselves, and the teacher is dragged down by the events, soon there will be a trace of his pedagogical and educational influence [12]. The teacher's broad outlook, ability to find satisfactory answers to any question, ability to comment on the news, instills in students a sense of respect for him and the science he teaches. Involving students in the teacher's learning process, finding common ground, discussing various issues among all students, and approaching issues of ethics and behavioral culture correctly will also help to increase students' learning activity.

In conclusion, in order to increase the activity of students in the acquisition of knowledge, the teacher should have a wide range of knowledge in their field, conduct lessons based on interesting examples, instructive stories, life experiences and conclusions, take into account the interests of students during the lesson. will have to try to find answers to the questions. Also, the effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the widespread use of modern technical means of lessons, handouts will further improve the learning process of students. Each subject has its own aspects, of course, that attract students. There are many such aspects, especially in the specialty sciences, in our opinion. In order to increase the educational activity of students in specialized disciplines, the role of the studied science in human life and development, its role in the economy and potential of the country should be very well covered. Only then will the student try to study the subject in more depth.

Hence, the quality and effectiveness of the educational process is directly based on the interaction of teachers and students. Therefore, the teacher's main focus should be on the formation of learning motives in students.

REFERENCES:

1. Маслоу А.Г. Мотивация и личность. СПб. : Питер. 2016. 290 с.
2. Муслимов Н.А., Рахимов З.Т., Хўжаев А.А. Касбий педагогика. Дарслик. Тошкент “Ворис” нашриёти – 2020. 517 б.
3. Муслимов Н.А., Рахимов З.Т., Ҳамидов Ж.А. Касб таълими методикаси. Дарслик. Тошкент “Инновацион ривожланиш нашриёт-матбаа уйи”, 2020. 282 б.
4. Муслимов Н.А., Рахимов З.Т., Хўжаев А.А., Қодиров Ҳ.Ш. Таълим технологиялари. Дарслик. Тошкент “Ворис” нашриёти – 2019. 568 б.
5. Подымова Л.С. Инновационность субъекта образования в контексте модернизации высшего педагогического образования // Педагогическое образование: вызовы XXI века. – М.: МПГУ, МАНПО, 2015.– С.32-37.
6. Raximov Z.T. Pedagogik kompetentlik ta'lim jarayoni rivojlanishining muhim omili sifatida. // “Zamonaviy ta'lim” ilmiy-amaliy ommabop jurnali, 2019 yil, № 7-son, 3-8-b.
7. Raximov Z.T. Talabalarning ta'lim jarayonidagi kompetentligini rivojlantirishda muammoli ta'lim texnologiyacidan foydalanish zaruriyati. / “Zamonaviy ta'lim” ilmiy-amaliy ommabop jurnali. 2019 yil, № 1-son, 32-39 b.
8. Raximov Z.T. Development of students' learning-knowing competence in vocational education // “Current research journal of pedagogics” – 2021. – Vol-11. – P. 233-240.
<http://masterjournals.com/index.php/crjp/issue/view/35>
9. Raximov Z.T. Personality-oriented educational technology as a factor in achieving educational effectiveness // Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR) – Vol 10, Issue 10, October, – 2021. – P. 920-929. <https://tarj.in/images/download/ajmr/AJMR-OCTOBER-2021-FULL-JOURNAL.pdf>
10. Raximov Z.T. The importance of biological and psychophysiological factors in the development of educational and cognitive activities // ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – Vol. 11, Issue 10, October – 2021. – P. 1614-1623
<https://saarij.com/wp-content/uploads/paper/ACADEMICIA/2021/FULL-PDF/ACADEMICIA-OCTOBER-2021/10.241,%20Zokir%20Toshtemirovich%20Raximov.pdf>
11. Рахимов З.Т. Факторы развития учебно-познавательной деятельности // Наука и образование сегодня. Научно-теоретический журнал. – Москва, 2021. – № 9 (68). – С. 43-49.

12. Управление учебно-познавательной деятельностью студентов в процессе обучения [Электронный ресурс] / В.Н. Зайченко. URL: http://vuzirossii.ru/publ/upravlenie_uchebno_poznavatelnoj_dejatelnostju_studento_v_v_processe_obuchenija (дата обращения: 08.03.2018)